

Yuvan pidika: An introductory review W.S.R. to acne vulgaris

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Abstract

In today's world, the personality of a person is first assessed by his looks and the beauty of the face is the prime attraction. Beauty of the face creates a sense of pleasure to sight. Although the beauty of face is important to all but it is of prime concern to adolescents. Yuvan Pidika is one such disease illustrated in Ayurveda which affects the beauty of face. This disease has been described under kshudraroga in many classical texts. Yuvan Pidika is characterized by symptoms like swelling, pain, redness, itching etc. caused due to vitiation of Kapha, Vata, Rakta dosha. Yuvan Pidika can be correlated with Acne Vulgaris in modern science. Acne is a chronic inflammatory condition of the pilosebaceous follicles affecting 85% of teenagers and thus causing a great harm to psycho-social development of youth in this era. Thus, an attempt has been made to explain cause, expression and management of Yuvan Pidika in ayurvedic perspective.

Keywords: Facial beauty; Yuvan Pidika; Mukhdushika; Tarunyapitika; Acne

1. Introduction

Beauty raised its different definitions since the onset of mankind but has always remained very much connected with the good looks. Nowadays people are getting very much concerned about dashing looks and personality infect they have become the pros and cons of the same coin. Someone has correctly said that "Face is the index of body and mind" which expresses joy, sorrow, excitement, nervousness, anger, fear etc.

According to Acharyas, among 56 upangas, face is considered the most important. In today's era as well, face is thought to be the site of wholesome beauty. And Yuvan Pidika is such disease which is affecting the facial beauty from minor ailments to major scars and that to in the most crucial period of life, adolescence where the youths are highly concerned about How they look? Acharya Sushruta has described Yuvan Pidika as eruption resembling Shalmali thorn on the face of young men and women called yuva and its pidika is Yuvan Pidika [1]. Yuvan Pidika is characterized by Ruja (mild pain), Ghan sparsh (hard and firm to touch), Medogarbh (sebum filled inside it) and shape like Shalmali kantik (thorn) [2]. It is also known as Mukhdushika and Tarunyapitika.

Yuvan Pidika is well correlated with Acne Vulgaris in modern medicine. Approximately 80% of people affected by acne range between the onset of puberty and thirty years of age [3]. Along with increased demand of beautification, the problems are also increasing due to changed lifestyle and polluted atmosphere. Random use of cosmetics is producing adverse effect. Many therapies are opted by various systems of medicines for Acne vulgaris with their own limitations, remission and side effects. So safer, better and non-remission treatment is always sought for. In ayurvedic texts Vaman is the process described for vitiated Kapha and to subside Pitta dosha and pitta samsargaja doshas, Virechan karma is indicated. Property of Rakta is analogous to pitta dosha, therefore Virechan is also effective in Raktaja vikara.

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2. Disease Literature review

2.1. Vyutpatti (Etymology) [4]

Yuvan pidaka is composed of two sanskrit words Yuvan and Pidaka.

- Yuvan: The word Yuvan is derived from the root of 'Yu dhatu' by using 'Kanin Pratyaya' with it. The word Yuvan is used in the sense of adult or young.
- Pidika: The word is derived from the root of 'Peed Dhatu' by using. "Dvul + Tap Pratyaya" with it. "Peed" Dhatu is used in the sense of pain. The meaning of Pidika is a painful eruption.

Yuvan pidika = yuvan + pidika.

The term yuvan represents the adolescence and pidika occurs due to predominance of pitta in twak and rakta (local swelling).

2.2. Definition

“Shalmalikantakprakhya kaphamarutshonitae, Jayante pidika yunam vaktre yaa mukhdushika” (Su. Ni 13)

The Shalmali thorn like eruption on the face of a youth caused by Kapha, Vata and Rakta are known as Yuvan Pidika. They are also known as Mukh-Dushika [5].

Yuvan Pidaka in different languages:

- Sanskrita -Yuvana Pidaka, Yauvana Pitaka, Mukh-Dushika, Tarunya Pidaka.
- Hindi - Yuvanapidaka, Keel, Muhanse.
- English - Pimples.
- Latin - Acne, Acne Vulgaris.
- Gujarati - Khila.
- Punjabi - Keel.
- Tibetan - Aruha, Kitibh [6]
- In charak Samhita: Acharya charak while describing ekdoshiya shotha, has given a very detailed description of inflammatory and non-inflammatory swelling. Acharya charak has mentioned pidika in trishothiya adhyaya. He described that pidika occurs due to predominance of pitta in twak and rakta (Shramaand & Dash Bhagwan 2012)
- In shushruta samhita: Acharya sushruta has described the disease as mukh dushika. He described this disease under 44 types of kshudra roga in nidan sthan chapter13 [7].
- Vagbhat: Acharya vagbhat has described the disease in both ashtang sangraha and ashtang hridaya under 36 types of kshudra roga in uttar sthana (Guptkaviraj Atridev, 2005).
- Madhav Nidan: Acharya madhav has followed the view of sushruta and given it the name yuvan pidika. He described it under 43 types of kshudra roga (Tripathi, 1993).
- Sharangdhar Samhita: Acharya sharangdhar has described yuvan pidika under 60 types of kshudra roga and followed aachara sushruta (Damodar Pandit, 2008) .
- Bhav Prakash: Bhav prakash has also described it due to predominance of kapha, vata and rakta under kshudra roga. According to him it occurs in both males and females (Misa Brahma Shankar, 2010).

2.3. Nidana of Yuvan Pidika

Nidana(causes) are summarized as-

- Aharaj- Oily, Spicy, Ushna, Fatty, Fast Food, Alcohol, Cold Drinks causes the disturbance of Tridoshas.
- Viharaj- Atapasevan, Diwaswapna, Vegvidharan, exertion immediately after meal.
- Kalaj-The Vata and Kapha are vitiated by sheet kala and Ushana Kala vitiates Rakta Dhatu.
- Vaya- Mostly occurs in Tarunya or Yuwa Avastha.

- Mansik Nidan- Krodh, Atishoka, Chinta causes Pitta Prkopa, Vata Vridhi.

Various causes of disease 'Yuvan Pidika' in all the Samhitas have been mentioned as the ones causing vitiation of Kapha, Vata and Rakta. Acharya Bhavmishra has mentioned Swabhava [8] as the cause of the disease. In Sharangdhara Samhita, Sukradhatumala is considered the cause of Pidika and Vaktrasnighdata [9].

2.3.1. RUPA

Acharya Sushruta has described Yuvan Pidika as the appearance of pidika resembling Shalmali thorn on the face of young men and women due to the vitiation of kapha, vata and rakta. By emphasizing on its presence in young adults, he has also described the time of its occurrence [10].

In Ashtanga Hridaya, Acharya Vagbhata has described signs and symptoms as follows:

- Shalmali Kantakakara Pitika: The conical eruption which resembles with Shalmali Kanta is called as Yuvan Pidika.
- Saruja: Painful eruptions
- Ghana: Ghana means solid, hard or indurated. According to Kalyanakaraka the Pidika is due to vitiated Kapha.
- Medogarbha: Eruption is filled with the Meda. It occurs due to obstruction of the Medogranthi.
- Yuna Mukhe: Adults are usually affected. This word shows the site of origin of Pidika and time of occurrence of the disease [11].

2.4. Samprapti of Yuvan Pidaka

None of the ayurvedic texts describes the samprapti of the disease. The samprapti as observed can be explained as the vitiation of kapha, vata and rakta. These vitiated doshas vitiates Rakta dhatu which in turn further vitiates Meda dhatu. Vitiated Meda dhatu produces excessive mala and that is Sweda [12]. The excessively produced sweda stays in Lomkupa as it is the moolsthana of Swedvaha srotas [13]. The srotodushti of sanga type occurs leading to the expression of disease Yuvan Pidika.

2.4.1. Samprapti Ghatak

- Dosha - Kapha, Vata, Rakta
- Dushya - Rasa, Rakta, Meda
- Srotas – Swedavaha
- Srotodusti - Sanga
- Sthana – Twak
- Samutthana – Amashaya
- Marga - Bahya Marga

2.5. Chikitsa

Shodhana chikitsa and Shamana chikitsa are the two basic types of treatments mentioned in Ayurveda classics in treatment of almost every disease. Treatment of Yuvan pidika can be explained on the basis of these two as:

2.5.1. Samshodhana Chikitsa:

- Vaman (Emesis): Vaman is the prime process indicated for Kaphaja disorders. According to Acharya Sushrut particularly vaman is beneficial in Yuvan pidika

“Youvanae Pidikaswesh Visheshath Chardanam Hitam” (Su Chi 20/37) [14]

Acharya Vagbhata [15] and Acharya Chakrapani [16] has also indicated the process of Vaman for this disease.

- Virechan (Purgation): Virechan is specifically indicated for Pitta Dosa, or Pitta Samsarga Doshas. Acharya Charak has indicated this therapy for all types of skin disorders,

“Vatottreshu sarpi vamanam shleshmotreshu kustheshu, Pittottareshu moksho raktasya virechanam cha agre” (Ch chi 7/39) [17]

- **Nasya (Errhine):** Nasya is the process of giving medicine through nasal route. Acharya Charaka has indicated the process in Urdhvajatrugata Rogas. [18] Acharya Vagbhatta has also told to apply the process of nasya in the disease of Yuvan Pidika. [19]
- **Raktamokshana:** Acharya Vagbhatta and Acharya Chakrapani Dutta has advocated the process of Raktamokshana in Yuvan Pidika. Acharya Sushrut has indicated it for some kshudra rogas while Acharya Charak has also mentioned the process in the disease produced by aggravated rakta. It has been mentioned by almost all the acharyas [20].
- **Samshaman Chikitsa:** Yuvan Pidika has local spread over the face, the external applications have immediate impact upon its characteristic features of the as burning sensation, itching, etc. different preparations are prescribed for the topical use. Lepa proves very effective when used simultaneously with internal administration of the drugs. [21]. Various types of lepas and oral medications are as

The paste of Vacha, Rodhra, Saindhava mixed with Sarsapa [22].

The paste of Dhanyaka, Vacha, Lodhra and Kustha [23].

The paste of Lodhra, Dhanyaka and Vacha [24].

Saarivadi Vati

Guduchyadi Vati

Shalmaliyadi Lepa

3. Conclusion

Yuvan pidika, a beauty disfiguring disease occurs in young adults ranges from minor pidikas which left untreated could result in major permanent scars on face. All the acharyas have mentioned its occurrence due to vitiation of Kapha, vata and rakta doshas. There are different types of shodan and shaman treatments prescribed for it as Vaman, Vivechan, Nasya, Raktamokshan, Lepa and some internal medicines.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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